

Synthesis of Substituted Thiazolo[3,2-a]quinazolines

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1,2-Dihydro-5H-thiazolo[3,2-a]quinazolin-5-ones with carboxy, carbmethoxy or carbethoxy group in position 2 (IX) have been synthesised by the condensation of ethyl-anthranilatethiocyanate (I) as well as 2-mercapto-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (III) with α,β -dibromopropionic acid or its esters (IV). The products by both the routes have been found to be identical. The structure has been established on the basis of analysis and pmr of one of the compounds.

SOME work has been reported¹⁻³ on the synthesis of thiazolo-quinazolines. We wish to report the synthesis of some new thiazolo[3,2-a]quinazolines with carboxy, carbmethoxy or carbethoxy group in position 2 (IX). These have been synthesised by the condensation of ethylanthranilatethiocyanate (I) or 2-mercapto-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (III) with α,β -dibromopropionic acid or its methyl or ethyl esters (IV).

It was reported earlier^{1,2} that the amine thiocya-

nate (I) changes to the thiourea of the amine (II) on heating and since, in this case, there is formation of 2-thio-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (III), 2-carbe-thoxyphenylthiourea (II) could be the intermediate. The intermediate thiourea (II), formed *in situ*, might react with vicinal dihalo compounds (IV) leading to the formation of linear product VIII or angular product IX or both. But we could isolate one compound only, as evident by tlc, to which we have assigned structure IX on the basis of pmr.

Fig. 1

IXc which has a thiazole ring with carboxy and dimethyl groups like that of penicillin showed in its PMR* (in DMSO- d_6) a multiplet (4H) at 7.3-8.2 assignable to four aromatic protons. It also showed a singlet (3H) at 2.6 due to three methyl protons (R'). Another singlet (4H) appeared at 3.45 which could be considered as due to overlapping of signals of three methyl protons (R'') with one methine proton at position 2. This down-field shift of three methyl protons may be attributed to its vicinity to the aromatic ring. The carboxylic acid proton appeared as a broad signal at 12.6.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin liquid bath and are uncorrected. PMR was recorded on Varian EM-390 90MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference.

*2-Carbomethoxy-1,2-dihydro-5H-thiazolo [3,2-*a*]quinazoline-5-one (IXa)*; $R = R' = R'' = H$; $R''' = CH_3$:

Method A: Ethylanthranilatethiocyanate (1.5 g) was mixed with methyl α,β -dibromopropionate (15 g) and the contents were heated in an oil bath at 120°. After half an hour, a clear solution was obtained, followed by separation of a solid. It was cooled, the product collected under suction and identified to be 2-thio-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (m.p., m.m.p., R, value and superimposable ir spectrum with an authentic sample).

In another experiment, the temperature was maintained at 120° for half an hour and then gradually raised to 150°. In this case, the quantity of 2-mercapto-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline went on increasing with time for 2 hr after which it went on decreasing with the simultaneous separation of a solid as evident by tlc. The heating was continued for 3 hr more to complete the reaction. The reaction mixture was cooled and the product collected under suction. It was crystallised from ethanol into white needles, m.p. 254°, yield 61%.

Method B: 2-Mercapto-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (1.5 g) was mixed with methyl α,β -dibromopropionate (15 g) and the contents heated in an oil bath at 150° for 2 hr. After cooling, the product was collected under suction. Crystallisation from ethanol gave white needles, m.p. 254°, yield 80%. The product was found to be the same as in 'A'.

The other compounds of the series except IXc were also prepared by method B. The data regarding the yields of these compounds, their m.p., solvent for crystallisation and analytical results are tabulated in Table 1.

*Chemical shifts given in this paper are in δ (ppm).

TABLE 1—THIAZOLO[3,2-*a*]QUINAZOLIN-5-ONES

Com- pound	R	R'	R''	R'''	Yield %	m.p. °C	M.F.
a	H	H	H	CH ₃ -	80	254	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ O ₂ S
b	H	H	H	C ₂ H ₅ -	77	248	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₂ S
c	H	CH ₃ -	OH ₂ -	H	50	283	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S
d	H	H	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂ H ₅ -	38	205	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
e	CH ₃ -	H	H	CH ₃ -	51	272	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₂ S
f	CH ₃ -	H	H	C ₂ H ₅ -	48	274	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₂ S

Compound a, b, c, e and f were crystallised from ethanol while compound d was crystallised from glacial acetic acid. All the compounds except c and d were isolated in the form of their hydrobromides.

Satisfactory elemental analysis for the above compounds were obtained.

2-Carbethoxy-1,2-dihydro-1,1-dimethyl-5H-thiazolo [3,2-*a*]quinazoline-5-one (IXc): A solution of α,β -dibromo- β,β -dimethylpropionic acid (1.30 g; 0.05 mol) in ethanol (15 ml) was mixed with a solution of 2-mercapto-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (0.90 g; 0.05 mol) in 100 ml of the same solvent. The contents were refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hr, cooled and the product collected under suction.

The mother liquor was concentrated when a further crop of the product was obtained. Both the compounds were crystallised separately from ethanol and were found to be identical.

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